

Critical Success Factors in e-Learning in Higher Education- Learner Perspectives

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Abstract

Distance learning has been gaining much ground in the developed world evidenced by the mushrooming of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs). This approach to learning has proven to be flexible and promoting the students, teachers, and university virtual mobility across the world. In the developing countries, additional effort towards further autonomy from external suppliers is needed owing to the different technical and socio-economic backgrounds. However, there are signs of improvement in the adoption of e-learning tools in higher education in developing countries, though still low and reliance is on the learning management systems. Considering that the educational experiences are created by the involvement of multiple stakeholders including teachers, institutions, employers and students, the study focused on the voices of the latter in exploring the critical success factors of e-learning. The study was underpinned by the lens of Moore's Theory of Transactional Distance. A qualitative approach was used. The findings of the study are expected to enhance the decision-making process by the higher education leadership, policy makers and by academics in the provision of e-learning.

Key Words: *learning design, e-learning, Transactional distance, learners' voices, Universal Design*

Dedication

To my daughter, Tariro Natasha,

for she would in years to come, understand why I deprived her of that motherly connection in the greater part of 2017

&

To my mum, Maria Chikerema:

To your health

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Acronyms

CSF	Critical Success Factors
F2F	Face to Face
HU	Hermeneutic Unit
ICTs	Information and Communication Technologies
LMS	Learning Management System
MEd-HE	Master of Education in Higher Education
PD	Primary Document
TD	Transactional Distance
ToD	Theory of Transactional Distance

Chapter 1: Introduction to the study

The contemporary era has seen the blossoming need to access higher education by a diverse population owing to the demand of knowledge based workers(BATES, 2015); and as a way of realising the potential to move around and access the changing employment markets globally (Koul and Kanwar, 2006, p. 5). As discussed in Chikerema, Chikari, & Chikerema (2016) the higher education institutions are now responding to the shifting landscape through e-learning implementations. The responsiveness stride is a consequence of the globalisation effect and technological changes affecting the globe and the varied demographic factors of the learners enrolling in the higher education sector. It cannot go unmentioned that the globalisation and the knowledge-economy (k-economy) have direct impact on the character and functions of higher education as evidenced in the following extract:

“...the shift from product based economy to a knowledge- based economy would result in an increased demand for knowledge workers who are capable of higher-order thinking and reasoning in solving intricate and authentic problems in the work place. This change would necessitate organisations to educate and train anyone, anytime and from anywhere” Govindasamy (2002, pp. 287–288)

Consequently, organisations are doing all they can to continuously professionally develop their workers. On the other hand, individuals are also gasping to up skill themselves. To that effect a typical contemporary learner can be a working mother in need of furthering her education. She should balance the family, school, and work commitments. As such, institutions of higher learning are taking advantage of the technology advancement to accommodate adult learners found in similar situations by enrolling them in a more flexible learning mode.

The adoption of e-learning initiatives in higher education seeks the reduction of the fees and at the same time attracting a wider and diverse learner population owing to its flexibility. In

addition Sapp and Simon (2005) suggest that it is cheaper for institutions of higher learning and such initiatives affords them access to untapped markets, hence increasing the tuition revenues (p. 471). In the same vein, Gulati (2008)in (Bhuasiri *et al.*, 2012, p. 844) argues that in the developing countries, the objective of e-learning is to reach many as opposed to developing a knowledge economy and lifelong education in developed countries.

Despite the growth of e-learning initiatives, their implementation has proven to be risky due to the inherent costs and low adoption levels (Ettinger, Holton and Blass, 2005; Sawang, Newton and Jamieson, 2013). Similarly, Wu, Tsai, Chen, and Wu (2006) posit that attracting and retaining learners in e-learning environments poses a challenge in higher education institutions and the cause is yet to be understood by researchers and educational administrators. In this regard, the study acknowledges that in the developing countries, additional effort towards further autonomy from external suppliers is needed owing to the different technical and socio-economic backgrounds.

In the context of e-learning in the developing countries, Bhuasiri *et al.* (2012) conducted some comparative analysis research on CSF in e-learning between the Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) experts and faculty in twenty (25) developing countries. From the ICT experts' perspectives, the CSF of e-learning are learner characteristics whereas for the faculty it is the infrastructure and the system quality. The scholars cited the need by the institutions in the developing countries to understand what drives the learners and faculty toward e-learning. Based on the recommendation by Bhuasiri *et al.* (2012), the current study explores the key predictors of e-learning success based on the learners' perspectives as key stakeholders of the educational services. The study is grounded in the developing country context with focus on Botswana higher education. The remainder of the document discusses

the background study, the problem statement, theoretical perspectives, research objectives, research questions, limitations, delimitations, ethical considerations, methodology, and significance of the study and highlights the provisional chapter outline.

1.1 Background Study

The advent of ICTs has facilitated the access to electronic information from varied sources including libraries, journals, presentations, and newspapers. As such, [Abdullah, Ward, and Ahmed \(2016\)](#) and [Bates, n.d. \(p. 13\)](#) state that ICTs have transformed the way we communicate, relate to each other, and learn. However, [Garrison and Anderson \(2003\)](#) argue that the ultimate goal of education is not about the information explosion, but it's about the cultivation of necessary critical, thinking and lifelong learning skills needed to manage the information that is available to learners. The digital lifestyle of a higher education contemporary learner; the dynamism in technology developments; and the gospel that is shared by the technology vendors have contributed to the augmentation of e-learning to the traditional face to face teaching and learning approaches.

The term e-learning has been perceived in many ways by different scholars. [Khan \(2001\)](#) perceives e-learning as synonymous to various other terms including 'web based learning' and 'online learning'. [Urdan and Weggen \(2000\)](#) ; [Govindasamy \(2002\)](#); [Hussin, Bunyarit, and Hussein \(2012\)](#) perceive e-learning as electronic delivery of course content through a blend of CD-ROMs, different network types, videos, audios and interactive TVs. The latter definition of e-learning is from an instructional or transmission standpoint. On the other hand, [Olson et al.\(2011, p. 7\)](#) considers the term e-learning to broadly mean a combination of teaching approaches, technologies, and administrative practices. The definition is more on knowledge construction ([Salmon, 2011, p. 5](#)) . The definition e-learning by Salmon deliberates that it is a

teaching approach that makes use of technologies in achieving the educational goals. Otherwise the scholar gives emphasis that e-learning is just old wine in new bottles: where the old wine are the teaching approaches and the new bottle are the technologies. Much that has been done in traditional classrooms can be done equally well or better in online environments. In the same vein, [Bates\(n.d\)](#) posit that e-learning basically merits the use of pedagogical aspects employed in traditional classroom coupled with some technologies and addressing needs of the learner in an online environment in delivering the educational services

According to [Anderson and McCormack \(2005\)](#) e-learning has to be governed by ten principles including learner engagement, inclusion, curriculum match, innovative approaches, effective learning and formative assessment. The extent of the mix of these principles determines the ‘see-saw’ relationship between the e-learning design and the pedagogical efforts to be employed by the teacher towards reaching the potential of the project ([Anderson & McCormick, 2005; Salmon, 2011, p. 4](#)). According to [Belassi and Tukul \(1996, p. 141\)](#) there are key factors that govern the success or failure of an initiative and these are termed ‘Critical Success Factors’ (CSF). Some of these factors in e-learning initiatives include the instructional design which is very influential in the development of quality e-learning materials and learner engagement ([Ettinger, Holton and Blass, 2006, p. 211](#)). As such, e-learning is not an issue of harnessing the technologies but making sure that the e-learning design affords the learner opportunities for success. E-learning is not just about using videos, creating interactive activities whose structure the learners cannot follow but creating a learning experience that affords learners to achieve the educational goals and to develop critical thinking and lifelong learning skills. The necessary skills for a 21st century learner entails the effective use of technologies to communicate and collaborate with the learners. Equally, the identification of the communication medium to use with learners is also important. For some learners’

communication through their phones, email, desktop conferencing, chats and bulletin boards might be ideal whereas for some that would be a form of social absence as they may prefer a tutor on-call. It is imperative that content developers address these varied needs in keeping the learners engaged (Ettinger, Holton and Blass, 2006; Fatimah. Hussein, 2009). It takes the learner to just close the laptop or the device that he /she uses for him/her to be disengaged. As such the appropriate choice of technologies that cultivate engagement need to be put into consideration. Ettinger et al.(2006, p. 211) argue that “Unless the materials become more creative, dynamic and engaging in their format and content, then e-learning is not likely to succeed with the coming generations”.

The potential of the technology is understood though it is decelerated by the failure to rethink the educational approaches (Garrison & Anderson, 2003, p. 56). The Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and e-learning content developers need to take into consideration the learner needs, preferences and profiles otherwise the learning will be unsuccessful (Waight and Stewart, 2005, p. 340; Sharma, Pandit and Pandit, 2011, p. 426; Hussin, Bunyarit and Hussein, 2012). In acknowledgement, Liaw et al.(2007) posit that understanding the learner attitudes contributes to the promotion of learner autonomy and development of problem solving skills in learners, thanks to the presence of the teacher in guiding the insights and cognitive skills in the e-learning environments. The way the technologies in a e-learning environment are appropriately used has a bearing in the development of digital literacies that the learners gain at the end of the course or programme.

Considering the investments by organisations and institutions in e-learning endeavours, the issue of high rate of drop outs cannot go unmentioned. Some of these are triggered by the content relevancy (Fatimah. Hussein, 2009; Zaharias and Poylymenakou, 2009), levels of

technological literacy, levels of technology support and above all the usability of e-learning designs (Zaharias and Poylymenakou, 2009). E-learning content relevancy in this study is taken to mean the relevancy of the material, assessments, and course objectives. On the other hand, Hotrum (2005) alludes that the design factors, lack of motivation and learning style mismatch are amongst causes for learner attrition. However, Ettinger et al.(2005) posit that the way the learner perceives e-learning is of importance. The scholar alludes that the perceptions stem from the way the activities are designed. In acknowledgement, Garrison and Anderson (2003, p. 56) posit that the quality of learning is promoted by how the content expert and the teachers design the learning experience.

1.2 Problem Statement

E-learning is at the core of business plans and institutions of higher learning with the widely used technology being the Learning Management Systems (LMSs) such as Blackboard, WebCT and Desire2Learn (Downes, 2005). However, the e-learning growth rate (then pegged at 35.6%) has failed to reflect the expectations on its usefulness (Wu *et al.*, 2006). Despite having an impressive plethora of literature on Distance Learning, Phipps and Merisotis (1999) posit that there are gaps to the quality of research that renders the findings inconclusive. Some of the gaps that warrant further investigation included:

- i. The existing research focusing on individual courses
- ii. The research not grounded on theoretical or conceptual framework
- iii. The research not taking into consideration how the use of technologies is influenced by the learning styles and tasks
- iv. The research excluding the dropouts in the research, focusing on those who are successful

Similarly, very limited research on e-learning is carried out in the developing world where the context is different from that of the developed countries. The potential of e-learning might even look paradoxical in the developing countries owing to the limited research on e-learning critical success factors depicting the context. [Siaciwena and Lubinda \(2008\)](#); [Gulati \(2008\)](#) argue that in the developing world, the constraints to e-learning implementations include the inadequacy of infrastructure, lack of skilled online tutors and content developers, the initial costs of technology for e-learning, lack of policies to guide the mode of education implementation and development.

Similarly, the contemporary society has a client centred culture which in educational settings translates to learner centred culture ([Downes, 2005](#)). The scholar alludes to the fact that the learner centred type of culture is not about only addressing learning styles and changing fonts sizes and background colours, but, it's about learner autonomy coupled with active engagement, changing the roles of teachers and learners. In acknowledgement, [Dockett\(2016\)](#) argues that unlike in face to face (F2F) environments where teachers and learners know their roles, they are yet to determine their new roles in online settings.

Several studies have been done on student perspectives of e-learning adoption, however, approached from the Technology Acceptance Model taking a techno deterministic stance ([Asoodar, Vaezi and Izanloo, 2016](#)) . Some the scholars included [Abdullah et al.\(2016\)](#) who suggested that one's experience in technology has a direct effect to the intentions and actual usage of the technology. The finding was seen to be linked to other factors such as self-efficacy and enjoyment. Such approaches focus on technology adoption from an individual perspective neglecting that the individual is a social being whose behaviour can be influenced by the social. Learning happens in a social context that warrants the understanding of the interaction of the

involved parties. In a typical educational environment interaction can be three-fold: learner-learner; learner-teacher; and learner-content. In a distance learning setting, these can be technology mediated. It is in this regard that this study finds the techno deterministic approaches inadequate and unrealistic as interaction with the technology may not be the sole predictor of adoption, later actual usage of e-learning systems. In acknowledgement Sun, Tsai, Finger, and Chen (2008) suggests that the user is the one that makes the decision on adoption. Such a decision is based on the experiences that one has during learning influenced by the learner's perceptions of teaching and learning.

In the endeavour to attract learners with varying learning styles, backgrounds, cultures, characteristics, goals, attitudes and technology literacies, it is only relevant to understand the critical success factors for e-learning from the learner population: the key stakeholders. How the HEIs teachers design their course material has an unquestionable impact on the learner experiences in distance learning programmes. Interestingly, how the transition from traditional face to face to electronic learning is managed at design time and pedagogically is critical to providing an educational and exciting experience to their learners. It is in this vein that the study would like to understand the critical success factors from the voices of the learners and to explain the learners' satisfaction of the extent teachers bridge the geographic distance in the provision of e-learning.

1.3 Research Aim(s)

The study therefore was aimed at contributing to understanding the key factors that influence the success of e-learning in higher education institutions in the context of Botswana.

1.4 Central Research Question

What are the students' perceptions of the key success factors in distance learning?

1.4.1 Sub Research Questions

- i. How do learners' characteristics influence their perceptions of e-learning?
- ii. How do teachers' characteristics influence learners' perception of e-learning?
- iii. How does the psychological distance influence learners' e-learning perceptions?

1.5 Setting the scene: Botho University Context

The section sets the scene by introducing the institutions in Botswana offering Distance learning programmes and whose learners participated in the study. Botho University is one of the private tertiary institutions in Botswana. The institution offers a wide range of programmes at undergraduate and post-graduate levels. The University currently prides itself of a multi-campus system with a total of five campuses namely: Maun, Francis Town, Gaborone, Maseru, and Blended and Distance campuses. The latter was specifically designed to house distance learning programmes. Because of the Blended and Distance learning campus, Botho University has cast its nets to attract international learners; thereby diversifying the learner population. According to Downes(2005) such initiatives are driven by the changing demographics of the learners who have become “ digital natives” or ‘ n-gens”. Botho University is one of the few higher education institutions in Botswana that have invested in e-learning and are already implementing the online courses through the Learning Management Systems (LMS): Blackboard 9.1 since 2014. Pishva, Nishantha and Dang (2010) state that Blackboard is a web based LMS that assist the educational institutions in delivering, tracking, and administering a blend of class and online activities. The scholars argue that Blackboard version 9 has been enhanced in terms of social and collaborative tools, and the Web 2.0 enhances social learning capabilities such as blogs, journals, group tools and notification alerts.

Use of LMSs /CMS for Distance learning has become common practice in HEIs (Navimipour and Zareie, 2015). However, it is of interest to the study to acknowledge that LMSs do not engage learners per say, but the e-tutor does through the LMS tools such as wikis, discussion forums, and the blogs. The bulk of the learners enrolled in the distance learning programmes in HEIs are adult learners who, according to Galusha (1998) have to balance the competing priorities such as academic, work, and family obligations. In agreement, Harris and Mccloud (2015) state that learners often cite convenience, pacing flexibility and their work schedules as reasons for pursuing studies online. More so, for some of the learners it was their first time to study online and some were not technological shrewd. That transition from traditional face to face mainstream to online learning also plays a part in the learners' perceptions of what constitutes 'distance learning'. The study acknowledges that multiple forms of presenting the content to the learners was evident as the institution uses a mix of text formats, videos, audios, quizzes through CD-ROMs/ DVDs and the Internet.

1.6 Limitations

The study was to be carried out in two of the higher education institutions in Botswana namely Botho University and BOCODOL. However due to unforeseen circumstances granting of permission to enter BOCODOL took a long time that made it difficult to gather information from the potential participants from BOCODOL. Hence the study then focused on Botho University, increasing the difficulty to generalize the findings to other higher education institutions offering e-learning programmes because there are no two institutions that can be deemed equal. There are multiple factors that should come to play such as: leadership; learners' characteristics; varying expertise of the teacher population; infrastructure and technical expertise of both the teachers and learners. In acknowledgement, Bates (n.d.) argues that the learning environments vary with context, epistemological and philosophical view of what

consists learning. It will be left with future research to explore different learning environments and the sense of transactional distance given different technologies, communication media and a separate set of teachers and learners.

This was my first time to use a qualitative software in analysing qualitative data. The processes in the analysis might not be perfect. Similarly, the number of participants in qualitative research is very minimal and the findings may need further testing using a larger quantitative sample.

1.7 Significance of the study

With the emergence of globalisation, Internationalisation and evolution of knowledge society, developing countries cannot escape developing online programmes in higher education, hence the need to understand the factors that influence online learning success from developing world context. The study is aimed at contributing to this effect as it will increase the visibility of the e-learning studies in the developing world, particularly in Africa. The results of the study will also guide the policy makers and implementers, academics with interest in furthering the research and higher education leadership in their endeavours to adopt the e-learning initiatives

It is envisaged that the study will also benefit the learners and teachers as they are directly linked to distance education. By sharing their perception of distance learning, experiences and critical success factors, learners will expose the ills and the positives of the e-learning phenomenon allowing the teachers to redefine and rethink the way they are doing things and the choices of the communication media for the benefit of the all the stakeholders and mostly their learners. The results of this study are expected to guide the teachers and instructional designers in addressing the learners needs in different educational environments particularly designing for quality dialogue and allowing the programme structures to afford the learners the

autonomy that is needed in such environments. The study aids the stakeholders to understand distance learning from the learner's point of view. As reflective and reflexive practitioners, teachers are expected to benefit immensely from the study as the results will inform the design of the future classes that are conducted at a distance. The educational institutions will not be an exception, the expected results will make the leadership look in retrospect at what they have done and help them identify the action points for their initiatives to succeed.

The study will contribute to the body of knowledge of the theory of transactional Distance research and promoting rigor in the field of distance education. The fruits of this study will afford HEIs in similar contexts, an opportunity gauge the future of the e-learning phenomenon early and map the way forward for its success.

1.8 Provisional chapter outline

The outline of the chapter was as follows:

Chapter 1: Introduction of the study

The chapter will introduce briefly the problem being investigated

Chapter 2: The review of the related literature

The chapter discusses the knowledge as findings of research works done by other scholars in building the gap that must be reduced by the current study. In addition, the chapter discusses the under-pinning theories and how they influence the way the study was to be investigated

Chapter 3: Research Design and Methodology

The chapter described the research paradigm, methodology, approach, methods, sampling techniques to be followed in the study and how the data was to be collected and analysed

Chapter 4: Data presentation and Analysis

The chapter allowed for the presentation of the collected data, its analysis and establishing their meaning against the set research objectives

Chapter 5: Discussion, Conclusions, and recommendations

The chapter discussed the findings and establishes the relationships existent between the ToD constructs in context. In addition the conclusion and recommendations for future studies are stated.

1.9 Timeline

Table 1-1 demonstrates the study timeline of the completion of the stages in the research process of the study.

Table 0-1 Study timeline

Month/Year	Task	output
July 2016	Proposal writing	Initial draft proposal
August 2016	Proposal Submission and Correction of proposal informed by the formative feedback from the supervisor	Submission of corrected Proposal
October 2016	i. Refinement of Literature review chapter	Submission of <i>Chapter 1 and 2</i>
November 2016	Research methodology chapter /Pilot study	Submission of <i>Chapter 3</i> Instrument Development
November 21 2016	Application for Research permit: Ethical Clearance by the Ministry	Research permit Approved towards end of January 2017
Feb-May 2017	Data Collection and Analysis	<i>Chapter 4: Data presentation, analysis, and interpretation</i>

June 2017	Conclusion, recommendations, and report	<i>Chapter 5: Conclusions and recommendations</i>
Mid June 2017	Initial submission to the Supervisor	Draft Submission
End of June 2017	Revise the submission based on supervisor feedback	Submission of the corrected document on approval by Supervisor
End of August 2017	Final submission	

1.10 Summary

The chapter introduced the background of the study and the problem under investigation. The next chapter reviews literature related to the problem under study

Chapter 2: The Review of related Literature

2.1 Introduction

The chapter discusses the knowledge as findings of research works done by other scholars in building the gap that must be reduced by the current study. In addition, the chapter discusses the under-pinning theories and how they influence the way the study was to be investigated. Because of the chapter the systematization of the study variables is drawn.

2.2 E-learning and the related terms

There is a plethora of research articles that have be written on Distance education, Distance learning, online learning or e-learning with these terms used interchangeably. The use of the different terms for e-learning often leads to contradictory findings amongst the researchers (Moore, Dickson-Deane, & Galyen, 2011; Tsai & Machado, 2002).

Some typical examples include the work of Downes (2005) who suggested that e-learning currently takes the form of online learning without explaining where the two meet. E-learning has been perceived as the use of computer network technology to teach and to provide educational material to learners (Lee, Hsieh, & Hsu, 2011). The scholars added that an e-learning system has also been perceived as an information system that integrates the educational material in multiple forms through e-learning tools including online discussion forums, quizzes, and live chats. However, if e-learning takes the form of online learning then what is online learning? In answer to the question Palloff and Prat, (1999) suggested that online learning is the separation of the instructor and learner in *space and time* with connections through educational media. It would seem that Online learning was being used interchangeably with distance education as evidenced in Keagan (1990) in (Palmer, Collins, & Roy, 1996), where distance education was perceived as the “ quasi–permanent separation of teacher and

learner throughout the length of the learning process” (p. 4). On the contrary, Moore(1997) posited that *distance education* is not the geographic separation of the student from the teacher, instead it is the relationships that exist between the teacher and learner when the separation (in terms of space and/or time) happens. Moore states that it is a pedagogical concept. These relationships are shaped by the interplay of three clustered variables namely structure of instructional programmes, teacher-learner interactions (dialogue) and the extent of self-directedness of the learner (learner autonomy). Hence the interchangeability of the terms by authors becomes confusing. It then becomes very difficult for readers to resonate with researchers as differences that reflect where we draw the line are not clear, warranting common definitions and terminologies.

Ironing out the misconceptions of the terms is critical in ensuring reliability of communication amongst vendors, education fraternity and research community and acquaintance of their distinctive characteristics aids in the selection of appropriate educational solutions that can enhance the effectiveness of educational practices (Tsai and Machado, 2002). In this regard, the scholars explained their conceptions of e-learning, web-based learning, distance learning and online learning as shown in Box 2.1.

E-learning is mostly concomitant with computers and interactive networks simultaneously and the two should be significantly involved in the learning activity not just providing the learning content.

Web- based learning is related to where learning materials (not just activities) are provided through the web browser including when the materials are packaged on CD-ROM or other media

Online learning is associated with content readily accessible on a computer (including Web, Internet, CD-ROM or disks)

Distance learning involves interaction at a distance between instructor and learners, and enables timely instructor reaction to learners. The scholars argued that simply posting materials to learners is not distance learning

Box 0.1 E-learning basics

Source:(Tsai and Machado, 2002)

It can be noted there are inconsistencies in defining distance learning and online learning evidenced by the definition given by Moore(1997); Palloff and Prat (1999); Tsai and Machado (2002). In addition to the conceptual inconsistencies of online learning and distance learning, is the conception of e-learning. The varying conceptions of e-learning and its related concepts are a cause of concern in the research community. There is a consensus amongst researchers on some of the terms. Lee, Hsieh, and Ma (2011) concurs with (Tsai and Machado, 2002) on the e-learning definition. However, in this study,

e-learning is perceived as approach to teaching and learning based on the use of technology in supporting and enhancing learning.

2.3 Learning environment

Garrison and Anderson (2003, p. 56) posit that the quality of learning is promoted by how the content expert and the teachers design the learning experience. In particular to distance learning, Hulsmann(2004); McLoughlin (2002) argue that quality distance education is measured by the learner support investment. However, BATES(2015, p. 446) argues that for one to be able to design effective teaching, an effective learning environment that should serve as a basis for the creation of a learning design is a necessity. Canole (2012, p. 9) perceives learning design as a “ methodology for enabling teachers /designers to make more informed decisions in how they go about designing learning activities and intervention, which is pedagogically informed and makes effective use of appropriate resources and technologies. BATES (2015,) states that the typical components of a learning environment (varies with context and epistemology that drives teaching) from the perspective of a teacher include:

- i. Learner Characteristics (Experience, prior knowledge and skills, learning styles, diversity, learning contexts)
- ii. The content to be covered to meet the educational goals (Content goals, sources, structure, quantity/depth, activities)
- iii. Strategies for skill development in learners (thinking activities, discussion, skills goals, practical activities)
- iv. Strategies for Learner support (counselling, scaffolding, feedback, other learners)
- v. Strategies for assessing learning (projects, e-portfolios, tests, essays)
- vi. The necessary resources for learning (technology, facilities, assistants, my time) (BATES, 2015, p. 446)

The extent to which these are developed to address the needs of the online learner would undoubtedly determine the educational experience and the success of e-learning from the perspectives of the learner. It is this view that is expected to be the outcome of this study.

2.4 The determinants of Educational Experience

In traditional classrooms where the teacher and the student are in the same classroom, learner engagement happens through small or the whole group discussions; question and answer sessions; individual or group activities and through the interaction with the content. The online learners make sense of the community through meaningful interactions with the teacher, the peers and the content (Garrison, 2007; Garrison & Arbaugh, 2007; Hussin et al., 2009). Figure 2-1 illustrates the framework for educational experience in traditional or technology mediated environments. In both the traditional and online settings the engagement process is facilitated by the teacher. The role of the teacher in facilitating the necessary interactions so that pedagogical goals are met is critical. At the core of the educational experience framework are the interactions that drive the epistemic engagement. The figure 2.1 epitomizes the learner support, resources and teaching goals reflecting the criticality of moderation in the educational environments.

Figure 0-1 Framework for educational experience

Source: Adapted from (Bates, n.d., p. 446; Garrison, 2007, p. 62; Garrison & Arbaugh, 2007, p. 158)

Knowledge is a social construct whilst meaning is created at individual level. According to Garrison & Anderson (2003) the educational experience has a duality of purpose: firstly meaning is constructed from an individual standpoint; and secondly, the meaning is refined and confirmed at social level with peers. The scholars argue that this duality of purpose reflects the unified nature of the educational transaction with the teacher shaping the learning environment by creating the cognitive and social conditions necessary for reaching the educational goals. It is what the teacher does that influences the learners' responsibility to learn. It can be argued that this finding by the scholars is an implication of three learning theories: Bandura's social learning theory, Lev Vygotsky's sociocultural theory and Wenger's community of practice theory. These theories presuppose that knowledge construction is dependent on the social interaction with peers, teachers, values, beliefs, and guided learning amongst others.

In a traditional classroom setup where the teacher and the student are there face to face, the student does not have much control in terms of pacing, it lies with the teacher who has the control of what is being taught at every class session. Outside the classroom the learner regains his/her independence and has the power to control what he learns outside the classroom with the teacher. The learner can read ahead based on the course outline shared with the learners by the teacher. The teacher facilitates the discussions and probes the learners to enhance their participation, assigns the day's or week's readings. Formative feedback is communicated immediately by both the teacher and peers in the physical classroom owing to their proximity. This feedback loops until the desired goal of learning is achieved.

2.5 Teacher Immediacy

On the other hand, [Garrison & Anderson \(2003\)](#) state that e-learning affords the learner some control in terms of access to the information. [Garrison\(2007\)](#), posit that there is need for balancing the social presence (building up of relationships and interactions in the virtual environment) with the educational communication that includes the teaching presence and cognitive presence (learner's ability to develop meaning from knowledge gained in the course). [Anderson, Rourke, and Garrison \(2001\)](#) defines teaching presence as "... the design, facilitation and direction of cognitive and social processes for realizing personally meaningful and educationally worthwhile learning outcomes" (p. 5).

Frequent, timely and constructive feedback; sense of humour (e.g. usage of smileys and emoticons); audio files; profile pictures; politeness, collaborative tasks amongst others are critical in online environments as the teacher and the learner are geographically distant. These strategies promote the teacher-learner psychological and social proximity and interactions. [Garrison and Arbaugh \(2007\)](#) and [Sun et al. \(2008\)](#) posit that the teacher immediacy is critical in moderating and guiding academic exchanges. As such, the teachers can exercise their intellectual and scholarly leadership in diagnosing the misconceptions in the discourse through feedback. One of the key factors in e-learning success include the leadership that understands and is geared to support the e-learning team efforts and learning culture in providing a stimulating experience to the learners; the e-learning team technological readiness and the consideration of the adult learning theories in affording the learners not just the technological experience but a powerful and exciting learning experience ([Waight & Stewart, 2005](#)).

2.6 Critical success factors based on research

Volery and Lord (2000) conducted an online delivery survey to 47 Australian University students in one management online course and identified three e-learning critical success factors from the learners' perspectives. These included the *technology*, the *instructor characteristics*, and learners' *prior attitudes towards technology*. The technology dimensions included: ease of use, navigation, interaction levels and interface design. The instructor characteristics included the attitudes toward students, classroom interaction and the teacher technical competence. The study also identified the importance of the role of the teacher in learning. In concordance Arbaugh (2002) and Hussin et al.(2012) state that it is imperative that the teachers develop new methods to facilitate interaction in promoting learning, satisfaction, and achievement in e-learning environments.

Similarly, Selim (2007) carried out a study to understand the critical success factors of e-learning from the voices of learners from 37 classes with a total response of 538 from five modules. The findings identified and measured four critical success factors that included learner and teacher characteristics, technology, and support factors. The four were found to be having significant effects in e-learning success. Selim (2007a) in the endeavour to ground the findings of the previous study using a theoretical lens conducted the study with the same sample of 37 classes but with 900 responses using the Confirmatory factor model to measure the criticality of the measures. The results endorsed the four factors as critical with teacher factor coming out tops as alluded by Volery and Lord (2000) earlier in this section. Sharma et al. (2011) conducted a similar survey at the International Centre for Open and Distance Learning to Personal Contact Programs on learners. The scholars identified that whilst the learners had some technology shrewdness, the facilitators lacked interest in the program. The above discussion reflects that there is a consensus amongst scholars including Schullo et al.(2007);

Sharma et al. (2011); Selim (2007); Selim (2007a) in their research works epitomizing the teacher as the catalyst in student learning. According to Chang (2016) the teacher acts as the motivator and advisor in e-learning environments. Similarly Sun, Tsai, Finger, and Chen (2008) argue that teachers' proximity to the e-learning environment is influential to student engagement.

2.7 Systematization and Analysis Model

The section provides a view of the parameters (indicators) considered to be relevant in the analysis of the phenomenon under study. It provides the operationalisation of the constructs and measures that serves as the foundation of the study. These were drawn from the literature and are shown in Table 2.1.

Table 0-1 Systematization and Analysis model parameters

Parameter	Attributes
Instructor Characteristics (Volery & Lord, 2000; Selim, 2007)	Attitude toward student (Volery & Lord, 2000; Liaw, 2008; Chang, 2016), Technical competence (Volery & Lord, 2000; Zaharias & Poylymenakou, 2009; Sharma, Pandit & Pandit, 2011), (Soong, Chan, Chua & Loh, 2001) Classroom Interaction (Volery & Lord, 2000; Hussin, Bunyarit and Hussein, 2012) Teaching style (Volery & Lord, 2000; Selim, 2007) Encourage Interaction ((Volery & Lord, 2000) Teacher immediacy (Garrison & Arbaugh, 2007; Sun et al., 2008) Attitude toward technology (Sun <i>et al.</i> , 2008)
Student Characteristics (Volery & Lord, 2000; Selim, 2007; Sawang, Newton & Jamieson, 2013)	Technical competence (Soong, Chan, Chua & Loh, 2001) Motivation (Selim, 2007) Commitment (Selim, 2007) Beliefs (Liaw, 2007) Attitude towards e-learning (Selim, 2007; Sun <i>et al.</i> , 2008)

	<p>Technology experience (Volery & Lord, 2000; Hassan M Selim, 2007)</p> <p>Openness to learning(Sawang, Newton & Jamieson, 2013)</p> <p>Collaboration in interaction (Selim, 2007)</p> <p>Perception of content and system (Selim, 2007)</p>
Technology (Volery & Lord, 2000; Selim, 2007)	<p>Ease of access and navigability (Volery & Lord, 2000; Selim, 2007)</p> <p>Interface design (Volery & Lord, 2000)</p> <p>Support Interaction (Volery & Lord, 2000)</p> <p>Level of interaction (Volery & Lord, 2000)</p> <p>Technology quality (Sun <i>et al.</i>, 2008)</p> <p>Speed of Internet (Selim, 2007)</p>
Support (Volery & Lord, 2000; Selim, 2007)	<p>Institutional Support(technical support, computer availability, learning material accessibility and printing) (Govindasamy, 2002)</p> <p>Learner support (Govindasamy, 2002)</p> <p>Faculty support (Govindasamy, 2002)</p>
Course structure (Govindasamy, 2002; Sun <i>et al.</i> , 2008)	<p>Design, Social, Transition and Environment (Vealé, 2009)</p> <p>Course flexibility (Sun <i>et al.</i>, 2008)</p> <p>Course quality (Sun <i>et al.</i>, 2008)</p> <p>Content quality (Selim, 2007; Bhuasiri et al., 2012)</p>
Student Engagement (Selim, 2007)	<p>Quality of activities (Ettinger, Holton & Blass, 2005)</p> <p>Interactivity of communication media (Ettinger, Holton & Blass, 2006; Fatimah. Hussein, 2009)</p>
Culture (Aparicio, Bacao & Oliveira, 2016)	Individualism/collectivism

2.8 Review of the central theoretical perspectives

The section discusses the underpinning theory, its constructs and how they influence the way the study was to be investigated. These constructs are then analysed together with the ones discussed in section 2.7 in this document to derive a proposed conceptual framework for e-learning.

2.8.1 Theory of Transactional Distance

The study is underpinned by lens of *Moore's Theory of Transactional Distance (ToD)*. As discussed in section 2.2, *Moore(1997)* stated that *distance education* are resulting relationships that exist between the teacher and learner when they are separated in terms of space and/or time. Moore states that it is a pedagogical concept. Because of the geographic separation, there is a potential for psychological and communications gap between the teacher and learner that must be bridged. It is this gap that is called the *transactional distance (TD)* and is significant in distance education where the teacher and the learner are separated in space or time. It is this gap that leads to varied teacher and learner behaviours that affect teaching and learning process (*Moore,1997*). Just like in face to face learning environments, the contemporary learner enrolments in higher education have seen the heterogeneous demographics that have led to the varied learner behaviours. *Moore (1993, p. 23)* further suggest that the term transactional distance is a relative term as it varies within different distance education programmes. ToD is built on three variables namely: structure, dialogue, and learner autonomy.

2.8.1.1 Dialogue

One of the variables of transactional distance as considered by *Moore (1997)* is the **dialogue**. *Moore (1993, p. 24)* argue that dialogue refers to the purposeful positive and constructive interactions that are valued by both parties. Each party in the interaction is respectful, active listener, contributor and builds on the contribution of the other. The scholar further suggested that interactions can either be positive or negative, but dialogue deals with positive interactions. Moore's construct of dialogue emphasises the need of a distance education teacher to have a sense of encouragement to the distance education learners as they can easily get discouraged compared to the F2F learners.

Most online learners experience isolation unlike in F2F environments as they are distanced from their peers and teachers. In agreement with Moore (1997), Sapp and Simon (2005) suggest that interaction can reduce this sense of isolation. Similarly, Kalogiannakis and Touvlatzis (2015) posit that emotions in the learning process can be minimized by increasing dialogue amongst stakeholders. It can be stressed that not only should distance learners be afforded academic support and dialogue but also emotional, and psychological support (Vakoufari, Christina and Mavroidis, 2014). Consequently, the dual role of the teacher is therefore tuition and counselling (Chrysoula, 2009). Early identification of risks of isolation is important for institutions to support the learners in their study (Tudor, Penlington and Mcdowell, 2010). The scholars suggest that the learner’s perceptions and expectations are influential to learning, hence dialogue could be used explore the expectations and acknowledge limitations that may render the learner’s expectations unachievable (p.78). The predictors of learner perception include social and personal contexts as illustrated in Figure 2-2.

Figure 0-2 Predictors of learner perception

Adapted from (Tudor, Penlington and Mcdowell, 2010, p. 72)

Undoubtedly, it cannot go unnoticed that as part of distance learning, especially where pacing is the teacher led, the learners’ perception of a teacher (teaching presence) as shown in Figure

2-2 can be a source of isolation increasing the distance between the teacher and the learner (Dockter, 2016). The scholar suggests that the teaching presence can neither be created nor controlled by the teacher (p. 74), justifying the need to understand the perceptions and expectations of the learner. In acknowledgement, Kassandrinou, Angelaki, and Mavroidis (2014) posit that in as much as the teachers facilitate, foster and encourage interaction amongst peers and between teacher and learner, it is equally critical that the learners take responsibility in understanding the communication space in distance learning. Likewise, Moore (1997) states that the technology and communication media may allow for interaction but dialogue is dependent on the quality of the media and extent to which the potential of media can be exploited especially by the teacher. Moore argues that the more structured the communication media the less the possibility for dialogue with the instructor.

2.8.1.2 Structure

Course structure refers to the “combination and interdependence of specific elements that result in conveyance of the objectives and desired outcomes of instruction” (Vealé, 2009). The structure expresses the rigidity or flexibility of the programme’s educational objectives, teaching strategies and evaluation methods. The responsiveness to the learner needs also play a role in the determination of the programme’s flexibility (Moore, 1993;1997). The scholars claim that the **extent of structure** is influenced by the philosophy and emotional characteristics of teachers, learner characteristics and personalities, institutional constraints, and communication media. In addition to this finding, Vealé (2009) further explained that the course structure is influenced by the environment, design, social, and transitional factors as shown in Figure 2-3.

Figure 0-3 Course structure Model

Source (Vealé, 2009, p. 98)

The course structure model focused on a combination of the following five elements namely: course flexibility, organisation, syllabi, technology, and the evaluation for each of the broad categories of factors.

2.8.1.3 Learner Autonomy

The potential of the learners to own their learning is called learner autonomy (Moore, 1993). It is the extent to which a learner is independent of the teacher in determining and controlling the learning goals. In distance learning, facilitation of appropriate dialogue for the learners is a demanding skill (Moore, 1997). As Moore(2003) would put it, distance education is not about just transferring traditional pedagogy and structures and flavouring these with new technologies. Garrison & Anderson (2003) suggests that knowledge is constructed at individual

and at social level. Consequently, it is important that interaction and learner independence are balanced for learning to be achieved.

2.8.2 Diagrammatic representation of the ToD constructs

In the study, the three constructs are studied to have a holistic understanding of how each one of them influences the other in the endeavour to uncover the critical factors that affect e-learning success. The relationships of the three variables are shown in Figure 2-4.

Figure 0-4 The relationship of the ToD variables

Source: adapted from (Moore, 1972, 1973)

Kassandrinou, Angelaki, and Mavroidis (2014); Moore (1997) further explain that the extent of rigidity in structure decreases the learner autonomy (independence), thereby increasing the transactional distance. Based on Figure 2-4 it can be noted that the **learner autonomy** is dependent on the change in the levels of structure or dialogue. When there is a reduction in dialogue the structure increases,

Figure 0-5 Basic elements that Characterizes Moore's Transactional Distance constructs

<https://sites.google.com/a/nau.edu/learning-theories-etcs47-spring-2011/theory/theory-of-transactional-distance>

implying an increase in transactional distance. In such situations, the learner is required to be highly independent. The contrary would require less learner independence. In this digital era, the scope of the distance has been altered thanks to the technology and the teacher's competence to integrate technology tools in teaching and learning processes. However, the transactional Distance can increase owing to the nature of participants, rigid structure, infrequent dialogue and communication medium (Dockter, 2016). Some of the elements that characterize Moore's Transactional Distance constructs are shown in Figure 2-5.

2.9 Implication of Transactional Distance on Design

Quality of interaction: Consequently, Giossos, Koutsouba, Lionarakis, and Skavantzios (2009) argue that the transactional distance as defined by Moore should be viewed in three forms of interactions namely:

- i. Teacher-learner
- ii. Learner-learner
- iii. Learner-content

The scholars posit that the transactional distance is not just an environment attribute but it is the perceived experience in the teaching and learning process. This view reinforces the fact that these interactions as discussed earlier in this document are central to the determination of the educational experience. The course design should be seen to consider the cognitive, technological, and social elements in the structure of the course and allowing for learner independence in construction of the knowledge. It cannot be overemphasized that the teacher has a role to play in the learner's experience. In consequence, Wengrowicz and Offir (2013) acknowledge the need for the redefinition of the teacher's role in the endeavour to close the

transactional distance. Dialogue, in form of interactions, need be valuable to both parties: it should be of quality(Moore, 1997).

The design of activities: has been identified as one of the factors that affect e-learning success. The activities should be engaging, challenging , appropriate, clear and without distractions (Hotrum, 2005).

Context: Benson and Samarawickrema (2009) ; Hotrum (2005) argue that in as much as the transactional distance varies from one learner to another, one teacher to another including varying environments, the varied contexts in which learning happens have implications that need to be addressed in course design. In this regard Dockter (2016) suggests that understanding the learner perception of who is their teacher (*teaching presence*) is important. The scholar suggests that knowing the learner’s learning styles is important to allow the teacher to present the dialogue in a manner that does not increase the distance between the teacher and the learner. Having written communication throughout the course might not work for those learners who are auditory and so forth.

Similarly, Benson and Samarawickrema (2009) argue that courseware for use in different environments (such as home, lecture theatre or computer laboratory) need not be designed in the same way. There is need to consider the extent of the distance between the teachers and learners and amongst learners. According to Hotrum (2005), the transactional distance gets affected by the learning context. “The unpredictability of the learner context and the mediated relationship with the learner requires careful attention by the educational designer to detail which might otherwise be managed by the teacher at the time of instruction” (p. 2). At the core

of an educational design is the learner. It is imperative that the designers understand the learner experiences, learning styles, and prior knowledge of the learners.

Feedback channels : The multiplicity of feedback channels; immediacy and quality of both formative and summative feedback is key to guiding the user in the achievement of the desired learning goals (Hotrum, 2005).

Quality e-learning resources: In addition, Ettinger et al. (2006) argue that the learning design is important in designing quality e-learning resources.

2.10 Conceptual Framework

Based on the literature review and the underpinning theory, this section presents the conceptual framework for e-learning with reference to Moore's Theory of Transactional Distance and the systematization and analysis model presented in the literature review section. The rationale of the framework is that distance learning does not exist in a vacuum; it is moderated by the interplay elements that constitute a learning environment. These elements are illustrated in Figure 2-6.

Figure 0-6 Model of Transactional Distance based on Moore's Theory of Transactional Distance

Source: Adapted from Veale and Watts (2006) in (Vealé, 2009, p. 6)

The model by Veale and Watts (2006) originally had the dialogue within the course structure. However in this study the two are considered as separate constructs with the dialogue dependent on the design of the course, teacher and learner characteristics, training of instructors, subject matter, and by environmental factors (Moore, 1993, 1997). With reference to the latter, Benson and Samarawickrema(2009) argues that the teaching institution plays a

role in constraining the learner support through the e-learning policies, infrastructure, systems and procedures. Additionally, the adaptations from the original model included substitution of some of the attributes with the ones that apply in context.

2.11 Summary

The chapter reviewed the literature related to the problem under study. Based on the literature review and the theoretical framework underpinning the study a conceptual framework was developed.

Chapter 3: Research Design and Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter described the research paradigm underpinning the study, research methodology, and research design, research methods, sampling techniques to be followed and how the data was to be collected and analysed. The order in which these are presented is guided by the research onion in Figure 3-1.

Figure 0-1 The research Onion

Source: (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2008) in (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009, p. 108)

The circled options map the choices that have been made about the study from the philosophies to the way the data was collected and analysed. These choices are explained in more detail in the subsequent sections.

3.2 Research Paradigm: Interpretivism

A paradigm is basic belief system or worldview that guides the investigator, not only in choices of method but in ontologically and epistemologically fundamental ways (Guba and Lincoln,

1994, p. 105). In addition, the philosophical world views that influence the practice of research and have to be explicit from the onset as they reflect the researcher's orientation of the world and the nature of research that is being undertaken (Creswell, 2009, pp. 5–6). The Interpretive worldview owes to the writings of Immanuel Kant (1781) and Max Weber (1864-1920) amongst the philosophers who argued for subjectivity in search for truth. According to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2009, p. 110) , the subjective ontology “holds that social phenomena are created from the perceptions and consequent actions of those social actors concerned with their existence”. The school of thought epitomizes the importance of interpretations in understanding the world around us. This worldview gave birth to what we now call Interpretivism. In this school of thought, subjective meanings are socially constructed through the interactions with others(Creswell, 2003; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007). It is argued in this study that distance learning is a subjective phenomenon with the transactional distance between the teacher and the student at varying levels depending on the interactions between the two and amongst learners. Such interactions cannot be prescriptive owing to the varying learner and teacher characteristics. The fact is also echoed by Saunders et al. (2009) as they argue that social interactions are in a constant state of revision.

From the constructivist knowledge claim, it is assumed in this study that Distance education, e-learning and the transactional distance are real and they form the ontological aspects of the study. As Weber (2004) posit that in this worldview, there is the inseparability of the reality being observed and the observer. Epistemologically, the concern of this study is listening to the learner's voices as they narrate their experiences of interacting with e-learning environments to the inquirer. The interpretations by both the observer and the observed would help understand and explain this social and psychological reality of distance learning. The transactional distance cannot be measured using objectivist approaches; rather, the knowledge

about it is socially constructed through the understanding of the interplay of the involved actors. Each learner has his or her own truth to tell based on his/her experiences in interacting with the learning environment including the teacher, peers, and the content. In acknowledgement, Guba & Lincoln (1994, p. 106) posit that human behaviour cannot be understood without making reference to the purposes the human actors attach to the activities. It is therefore important that data be gathered from the source: the people concerned in the teaching and learning process as they share their experiences. In the study, focus is given to the learners' voices.

3.3 Research Approach

Mavetera (2011) argues that the use of theory is inherent in both the deductive and the inductive approaches to research. The deductive approach is inclined to theory testing whereas inductive approach is more into theory generation. The concern of this study is to understand and explain the transactional distance based on the learners' voices and then develop theory qualifying the study to be inductive in nature. Saunders et al. (2009) posit that inductive research allows for alternative explanations and seeks to understand the events in context.

3.4 Research Methodology

Marshall (1996) suggests that the research methodology should be chosen based on the research questions not according to the researcher's preference. The scholar argues that the quantitative research methodology should be followed when dealing with the '*what*' type of questions, whereas the qualitative research would be appropriate with the '*How*' and '*Why*' questions. Consequently, as the research paradigm is constructivism, and the study research questions fall in the latter category. The other reason that compels this study fall under qualitative research owes to the research paradigm followed in the study which is constructive. In a similar vein, it cannot go unmentioned that constructs for the Theory of transactional distance are qualitative

in nature as alluded to by Moore (1997). According to Hancock, Ockleford, and Windridge (2009), qualitative research helps understand the way things are in the social world. Similarly, Kaplan and Maxwell(1994) support Hancock et al. (2009) in that qualitative research seeks to understand the perspectives and behaviour of people and the contexts in which they act.

3.5 Research Design

A research design is a plan or proposal to conduct research encompassing the philosophical, methodological and methodical assumptions (Creswell, 2009, p. 5). Creswell (2014) argues that it is not enough to select a research approach without considerations for the research design. The scholar argues that these are types of inquiry that provide specific direction for procedures. He argues that some call it strategies of inquiry. The study research strategy is the Case Study. Myers (1997) posits that the term ‘case’ has multiple meanings including being used as a unit of analysis or to describe a research method. Yin (2003) in Baxter & Jack (2008, p. 545) posit that a case study design can be used in the following situations:

- i. To answer the ‘how’ and ‘why’ questions
- ii. Where the behaviour of the participants cannot be manipulated
- iii. The focus is to cover contextual conditions
- iv. The boundaries are unclear between the phenomenon and the context

The first three conditions apply to the study because first one is addressed in section 3.3 as the reason the qualitative approach was followed; the second one is addressed in section 3.2 where the study paradigm seeks to understand the subjective experience of the learners, one cannot control how the learners behave but the behaviours are governed by the interplay of the people and the learning material. The third situation applies as the study seeks to understand the critical success factors in e-learning from an African context, with mention of Botswana.

The case study type to be followed in is the single where the number of cases to be considered is only one. The unit of analysis in this study is the learner. The study would like to find out what factors make e-learning successful from the learner's standpoint in an institution of higher learning.

3.6 Population and sampling

The following sections informed more on the population, sample, sampling strategy, and the sample size.

3.6.1 Population

The research population covers learners currently enrolled for postgraduate distance learning programme: MEd-HE at Botho University. The study population is one hundred and twenty-one (121) learners. The institution was selected purposefully largely owing to the ease of access of the population.

The target population graduate programme was purposively selected based on the following reasons:

- i. The Faculty of Research and graduate studies houses programmes that have been running in online mode longer than the rest of the programmes at Botho University.
- ii. Furthermore, the lecturers in the department have pedagogical expertise to teach face to face classes and online programmes. However, how the teachers' pedagogical and technological competence influence the facilitation and the learners' perspectives in e-learning motivated the study too.

3.6.1.1 Sampling and Sample Size

Yin (2009) argues that the sample size criteria in case study research has no relevance as the ‘sampling logic’ does not apply. However, within the case study, the selection of the participants to be interviewed need to be bounded owing to the diminishing returns associated with qualitative data collection. Data saturation is the point at which the new data does not alter the code book, that is the new data is a replication of what already exist (Guest, Bunce and Johnson, 2006; Dworkin, 2012; Marshall, Bryan; Cardon, Peter; Poddar, Amit; Fontenot, 2013). The concept of “saturation” less helpful in estimating sample sizes prior to data collection (Guest et al., 2006). The scholars argue against limiting the sample size to a range between six and twelve especially for sample that include heterogeneous groups of participants. In this regard the study was focused on one group: learners. Guest et al. (2006) posit that homogeneity of a sample makes it faster to reach saturation and specifically within a sample size of twelve. The sample size is communicated in the following chapter

3.6.1.2 Sampling Strategy

The sampling strategy of the study is purposive sampling. Marshall (1996) argues that qualitative researchers believe that subjects cannot be selected randomly because some are ‘richer’ than others. The scholar argues that a judgment/ purposive sample allows the researcher to select the most productive subjects to answer the research questions.

3.7 Data collection methods and techniques

The study followed an interpretivist paradigm which in consequence underpins the qualitative research method that was used in the study. A mono method was used. According to Saunders,

Lewis and Thornhill (2009) mono method entails using a single data collection method(in this study qualitative) with corresponding (qualitative).

Semi structured in-depth interview was used as a data collection method to garner information from the participants. The in-depth interview was used so that the participants would be able to express their own stories, experiences, and perspectives of e-learning. In acknowledgement, Diccobloom and Crabtree (2006) posit that qualitative interviews are based on life experiences of the interviewees. The scholars argue that semi structured interviews use a mixture of pre-determined open-ended questions and those that emerge during the dialogue between the interviewer and the interviewee(s). Similarly Boyce and Neale (2006) argue that in depth interviews are intensive and are useful when one is seeking the understanding of behaviours or exploration of new issues in depth. The data that is collected using any interview technique include narratives, text, or images.

3.8 Data Analysis

In the earlier section 3.6.2.1, sample size was discussed and there was mention of the data saturation level. It is important to note that data saturation is reached not through the sequential stages of data collection and analysis. These two processes occur concurrently. According to Glaser and Strauss(1967) in (Gasson, 2003) the data collection, coding and analysis happen together and the decision on what data to collect next and where emerge. The interviewees in the study were asked to fill in consent forms (see section 4.9) in which they indicated whether they favour the interview to be recorded or not. In the case where the interviewee does not need to be recorded, the interviewer would gather the short notes on the interview, otherwise the interview was recorded using a Sony recorder affording the researcher time to concentrate on questioning, listening, and probing.

The software package that was used for data analysis is the ATLAS.ti 8. In ATLAS.ti all the data in different formats; from various sources, including codes, memos, annotations relevant to a project is stored in a container termed as the Hermeneutic Unit (HU). The advantage of the Hermeneutic Unit is that the data is accessible from a pivotal point making it easy to access and establish their relationships. The diagrammatic representation of a Hermeneutic Unit is shown in Figure 3-2.

Figure 0-2: Diagrammatic representation of a Hermeneutic Unit in Atlas.ti

Source: (Payambarpour, no date, p. 5)

The collected data was to be transcribed verbatim. The transcripts were then be coded into categories of what is observed and put into themes for analysis(Gasson, 2003). The codebook was monitored for any changes in the process to determine the data saturation level. The analysis process of the qualitative data follows the four steps namely open coding; axial coding; theoretical memos; and the selective coding (see Chapter 4 for more detail).

3.9 Evaluation of the quality of the study

The trustworthiness of this study borrows from the quantitative criteria of rigor and quality. According to Gasson (2003) the criteria used in qualitative-interpretive research include confirmability, dependability, internal consistency and transferability.

- i. “*Confirmability*: conclusions depend on the subjects and conditions of the study , rather than the researcher” (Gasson, 2003, p. 90). In the study, member checks would be done to enable participants to confirm the interpretations.
- ii. “*Dependability/Auditability* : The study process is consistent and reasonably stable over time and between researchers” (Gasson, 2003, p. 90). The triangulation of sources might have a bearing on dependability. In addition, the qualitative research methodology chapter that is presented in the study detailed the study process. That would aid the interested researchers to understand how the research was carried and understand the decisions taken thereof. In the case that they agree with these, there would be a likelihood of reproducibility of findings.
- iii. “*Internal consistency*: the research findings are credible and consistent, to the people we study and to our readers” (Gasson, 2003, p. 90). To increase credibility, the cases have been drawn from two institutions. The usage of varied perspectives from the three programmes is expected to increase credibility as findings are triangulated by the multiplicity of sources. These cases under study were drawn from the target population putting the expected findings to context.
- iv. “*Transferability*: how far can the findings /conclusions be transferred to other contexts and how do they help derive useful theory” (Gasson, 2003, p. 90). As argued in section 4.5 on the research design, a case study research does not follow a sampling logic. Hence the aspect of generalisation to other contexts might be very difficult to achieve as the samples in the qualitative research are very low. However, the findings would

help in generating a theory that might then need to be tested in other contexts for generalisations. The resources that are used in each context may vary, hence these when taken into consideration in other future researches may help endorse the generality of the expected theory.

3.10 Ethical Considerations

The study involved interacting with people including gatekeepers. Hence, it is inevitable to consider ethical principles. Prior to conducting the research, an ethical clearance from the *Ministry of tertiary Education, Research, Science, and Technology (Botswana)* was sought. Upon its approval, the research permit with ref number: E 1/20/2(10) (*see Appendix for more detail*) was issued. The permit was used to gain access to the participants.

The participants were not to be coerced into participating; consent *forms* were developed as a contract between the researcher and the participants. The consent form communicated clearly that the participant could opt out of participating as when they feel like. The principle of anonymity was also observed in the study, as the participants were informed that instead of their real names pseudo names were to be used in the documentation of the study so that the participants shall remain anonymous.

As way of making sure that the participants understand the nature of the study under investigation, the research problem and the purpose of the study was included as part of the instruments and in the consent form so that the participants had a clear understanding of what they were getting into and the benefits associated with the process.

Dicicco-bloom and Crabtree (2006) argue that in the process of in-depth interviews, participants may share information that may put their positions at risk; hence the need for anonymity, A clause on confidentiality was added so that participants are aware that there would be no victimization linking back to them. However, anonymity cannot be guaranteed holistically, as the researcher would meet face to face with some interviewees. After analysing the data, the study results would be shared with the participants and stakeholders.

3.11 Summary

The chapter discussed the approach that the study was to take from the philosophical assumptions, methodology, research design and methods. In addition, the data collection procedure and how the collected data would be analysed was also discussed. The next chapter discussed the actual process as it happened empirically.

Chapter 4: Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 Introduction

The Chapter allowed for the presentation of the collected data, its analysis and establishing the meaning of the analysed data against the set research objectives.

4.2 Data Presentation and analysis

Data collection and analysis happened concurrently to establish the saturation level. The presentation becomes evident as the gathered data is analysed and discussed. For this reason, the data presentation and analysis are also discussed simultaneously.

4.2.1 Participants Profiles

The participants were all from Botho University and pursuing a postgraduate degree in higher education. The additional profile details of the participants are as shown in Table 4-1.

Table 0-1: Participants' profiles

<i>First Interviewee</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Age: Forty-five (45)▪ Year of Study: 2nd▪ Modules Completed Successfully: 6▪ Employed	<i>Second Interviewee</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Age: thirty-three (33)▪ Year of Study: 2nd▪ Modules Completed Successfully: 6▪ Employed	<i>Third Interviewee</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Age: thirty-one (31)▪ Year of Study: 2nd▪ Modules Completed Successfully: 5▪ Employed
<i>Fourth Interviewee</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Age: thirty-three (33)	<i>Fifth Interviewee</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Age: thirty-four (34)	<i>Sixth Interviewee</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Age: Forty (40)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Year of Study: 1st</i> ▪ <i>Modules Completed Successfully: 4</i> ▪ <i>Employed</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Year of Study: 2nd</i> ▪ <i>Modules Completed Successfully: 6</i> ▪ <i>Employed</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Year of Study: 1st</i> ▪ <i>Modules Completed Successfully: 3</i> ▪ <i>Unemployed</i>
<p><i>Seventh Interviewee</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Age: Forty (33)</i> ▪ <i>Year of Study: 1st</i> ▪ <i>Modules Completed Successfully: 4</i> ▪ <i>Unemployed</i> 		

As reflected in Table 4-11 most of the participants were employed at the time of carrying out the interviews. In addition, they are adult learners who should balance their occupational, social, and family commitments. The gender balance is as shown in Figure 4-1 and Figure 4-2.

Figure 0-1: The network of male participants

As reflected in Figure 4-1, the first, second and fourth interviewees were male. D1, D2, and D4 denotes the order in which the transcribed documents were fed into the Hermeneutic Unit using Atlas.ti software.

Figure 0-2 The network of Female participants

The same representation principle applies to Figure 4-2 with the third, fifth, sixth, and seventh participants being female. The order in which these participants were accessed had nothing to do with gender but their availability for the interviews.

4.2.2 Sample size and saturation level discussion

The transcribed data was open coded and scientific constructs were created by the inquirer. The process was closely monitored to determine the saturation levels. As discussed in the preceding chapter that the sample size would be communicated once data gathering and analysis were done, it is at this point that we communicate that the sample size was seven (7). Initially the data was transcribed and initial open codes were developed from the analysis of the transcripts after the first participant was interviewed. The rest of the participants data followed an analogous process. The open coding for the first interviewee data generated thirty-three (33) codes. After the second interview data, the codes rose to fifty (50) with seventeen (17) new codes emanating from the second interview data. The third interview generated three (3) new codes with the rest echoing the codes from the earlier interviews. The data was then collected from the fourth and fifth interviewees and the codes rose to sixty (60) with three (3) and four (4) new codes respectively.

By the end of the fifth interview the code book changes had become minimal. The sixth interview data increased the codes to sixty-three (63) by adding three (3) new codes. The seventh interview data failed to modify the code book. Consequently, seven (7) became the number at which the saturation was reached. Hence the global view of the initial codes was sixty-three (63) as shown in Figure 4-3.

Figure 0-3: Code level after the seventh interview data

A glimpse of the codes generated from the seven interviewees data are reflected Figure 4-4.

Figure 0-4: Extract of the codes in the Hermeneutic Unit

4.2.3 Code Groups

The initial codes were all put in a code group called *global view* and resulted in the code network presented in Figure 4-4. Within the group, the codes were put into sub code groups informed by the underpinning theory: *Theory of Transactional Distance*. The sub code groups were named after the three overarching variables of the theory: *learner autonomy*, *dialogue*, and *course structure*. These three code groups were colour coded as shown in Table 4-2.

Group Name	Code	Group Colour	Code
<i>Course Structure</i>			
<i>Dialogue</i>			
<i>Learner Autonomy</i>			

Table 0-2 : Colour codes for the main groups in the Hermeneutic Unit

Within each sub code group some codes were merged and some were renamed resulting in a reduced number of codes in the Hermeneutic Unit. The number was forty-seven (47) (See *Figure 4-8*). Figure 4-5 to 4-7 shows the codes that were grouped into the course structure code group, dialogue code group and learner autonomy code group respectively.

Figure 0-5: Course Structure Code network

Figure 0-6: Dialogue Code Group network

Figure 0-7: Learner Autonomy Code Group Network

The learner autonomy group codes were not further grouped as the codes hardly had any commonalities. As such the codes in Figure 4-7 became themes for that group.

The data interpretation was done using the overarching groups and their interrelationship in turn. To gain more insight on the relationships between themes and within each code group and across code groups, axial coding was done guided by the quotations. However, the *Open Group Manager* tool in Atlas.ti 8 did not allow for a hierarchical arrangement of codes. Then additional code groups were created and named after the main sub groups (e.g. CS_Course Flexibility, CS_Course Interaction, and so on). These additional codes became the themes under a code group derived from the underpinning theory variables. Consequently, the code groups that the study had in the Hermeneutic Unit after the creation of the code group hierarchy were as shown in Figure 4-8.

Figure 0-8: Code groups in the Hermeneutic Unit

4.3 Course Structure

The course structure had five themes namely *course flexibility*, *course quality*, *course guidance*, *course orientation*, and the *technical support*. These are further analysed in the following sections.

4.3.1 Course Flexibility

Figure 4-9 shows a sample of a full quotation. Figure 4-10 shows the network with imported quotations and relationships amongst the codes within the course flexibility codes.

Figure 0-9: Sample quotation

Figure 0-10 : Course flexibility Code network with relationships and quotations

Figure 4-10 shows the code network for the theme course flexibility and some of the quotations in the group. For example, quotation 6:5 (see full quotation in Figure 4-9) shows the response from a participant that contributed to the code-named intermediaries' navigability.

On the course flexibility, the participants argued that one of the critical reasons they are taking online courses owed to their flexibility which allowed the students to participate in the course anywhere, anytime and on the go. This kind of flexibility was facilitated by the provision of

learning material in multiple formats. In a similar vein quotation 2:2 alludes that the flexibility of the course owed to the availability of learning resources 24/7 online. In concordance with quotation 2:2, Quotation 3:6 from participant three posited that the course allowed her as a mother of two to balance her family chores with the school work.

Quotation 6:17 (See Figure 4-11) remarks on the ease of access of the discussion forums. The Masters in Education- Higher Education programme at Botho University is offered online using Blackboard as the Learning Management System. Quotation in Figure 4-9 mentions the ease of navigation of Blackboard of which coupled with the flexibility in accessing the learning material contributed positively to the flexibility effect.

Figure 0-11: Expanded view of Quotation 6.17

The menu driven interface in Blackboard made the learners in the program find what they were looking for easily. According to the quotation in Figure 4-9, the nomenclature of the menu options was suggestive of what they were intended to do, hence it became easier to navigate the system. Cercone (2008) posits that the characteristics of adult learners include reduction in memory as they age and balancing career, family, and personal choices. The scholar argues that when it comes to memory reduction, the design of online learning programmes are

necessitated to adapt to addressing this using clear menu driven structures, search and find options including practice feedback. Cercone’s argument is commensurate with the findings in the study. The easy to use Blackboard menu reduced memory overload to the adult learners as the participants claim that they managed to interact with peers and tutors and to upload assignments without much cognitive effort. The availability of the learning resources made it possible for the participants to balance their school and work commitments. It is the flexibility in accessing the learning material, submission of assignments and engaging in collaborative activities online that one of the participants finds the course flexibility motivating for those who are working and studying simultaneously. Participant commented:

“Course flexibility helps in balancing my work, studies and my social time. The flexibility of distance learning course material helped me especially the videos. I could listen over and over again to the lecturer explanations where I needed basic understanding of the concepts. I would read more the self learning material to boost my understanding”

The quotation 3:19 points at the course not being 100% flexible as the course is teacher led.

A screenshot of a Blackboard discussion post. The post title is "D 3: Int_3 - 3:19 The distance learning that we did was not 100% flexible as it was teac... (5477:5831)". The content of the post reads: "The distance learning that we did was not 100% flexible as it was teacher-led with the teacher dictating the submission deadlines which were not changed unless one had mitigation conditions made it possible for me to manage my time. Though it was difficult, I never had a habit of finding excuses for not doing my work. For some this led to their downfall".

D 3: Int_3 - 3:19 The distance learning that we did was not 100% flexible as it was teac... (5477:5831)

The distance learning that we did was not 100% flexible as it was teacher-led with the teacher dictating the submission deadlines which were not changed unless one had mitigation conditions made it possible for me to manage my time. Though it was difficult, I never had a habit of finding excuses for not doing my work. For some this led to their downfall

Hence, quotations 2:11 and 1:10 from the participants posited that, the course structure should take into consideration the nature of learners that enrol in the program as they had at some point during the course, felt the pressure of having to meet deadlines of given tasks and at times

submission dates. On the latter, quotation 1:10 emphasises that the submission dates of assignments fell on the same date. Asked on whether the dates were given on time, the participant replied that the dates were communicated on time. The quotations in Figure 4-12 show that some participants claimed that they do have self-direction and discipline to account for their learning.

3 Quotations:

D 1: Int_1 - 1:23 am 100% confident in terms of managing my time, meeting deadlines and... (6408:6759)

am 100% confident in terms of managing my time, meeting deadlines and taking full responsibility of my learning. This is because my philosophy is that each and every student has to take full responsibility of their learning. Excuses do not benefit anyone, therefore, I never waste my time by advancing excuses as to why I cannot meet academic deadlines

D 7: Int_7 - 7:13 I am now an independent learner as I can research on m,y own. The cour... (2307:2398)

I am now an independent learner as I can research on m,y own. The course does not spoonfeed

D 7: Int_7 - 7:14 I am confident.I have my persona timetable for the studies (2402:2459)

I am confident.I have my persona timetable for the studies

Figure 0-12 Accountability for own learning

4.3.2 Course Quality

The course quality theme was informed by the network in Figure 4-13.

Figure 0-13 : Course quality Code network with relationships and quotations

Another aspect that the participants enjoyed about their online course was the course quality. The course quality was expressed through the quotations from the transcripts that mentioned factors such as the skills and abilities that the course equips them with. As participant 2, through quotation 2:25 expressed that the course had fostered the innovative, creative, and analytical thinking skills. This was echoed also by the following quotation 1:7

D 1: Int_1 - 1:7 It is pre-dominantly individual because each student tackles an array... (1319:1784)

It is pre-dominantly individual because each student tackles an array of assignments by themselves, (2) it challenges an e-learner to conduct research in order to find further information. (3) Some questions require students to apply critical thinking and analytical skills. For instance, one of the assignments specifically required students to critically analyse a document. In another task, we had to solve a problem by actually designing a programme of learning.

Figure 0-14: Expanded view of quotation 1.7 extracted from the network report

For some it gave them a challenge and as such the course was enriching. One of the interesting points that one of the participants is expressed in the quotations 2:10 and 1:19 expanded in Figure 4-15 and Figure 4-16.

Quotation	Show in document
2:10 The good thing about this course was that it fell within my field of s	
The good thing about this course was that it fell within my field of specialisation and although at times it was really hectic, I just managed to held on because I knew that it was value-adding to my personal growth.	

Figure 0-15: Full view of Quotation 2.10

Quotation	Show in document
1:19 Be that as it may, online studies require that each student must be se	
Be that as it may, online studies require that each student must be self-disciplined and committed towards their studies. Otherwise, external motivation is only secondary form of motivation. However, I have discovered that students only take all components of their studies seriously if the components add value to their overall performance as in continous assessment.	

Figure 0-16: Full view of Quotation 1:19

The quotations endorse that what motivates them as adult learners in pursuing the course despite its challenges is the value addition in professional development. Also from quotation 1:19, the value that the task or activity adds is what drives their participation. This confirms quotation 4:11 that mentioned that “the thought provoking topics that the tutors paused to learning during the course kindled their appetite for learning and re-learning”. As part course quality, participant 6 had this to say:

 D 6: Int_6 - 6:3 The course flexibility allows for the material to be presented in diff... (865:1295)

The course flexibility allows for the material to be presented in different format to address diverse learner needs coupled with the content quality will definitely motivate learners as they will really feel that they have value for their money. When content quality is poor it defeats the purpose of having multiple presentation formats and it doubles the sense of isolation as the attitude toward the material is already negative

4.3.3 Course guidance

The course guidance theme had the codes reflected in Figure 4-17. These had all to do with the clarity of course materials, learning outcomes, questions, and instructions that are shared with the learners at various points in the learning process. Some of the quotations that were elicited from the participants included the ones expressed in quotation 2:22, quotation 5:15 and quotation 6:1 in Figure 4-18. As these were post-graduate learners, and some of them practicing teachers, they valued clarity in the learning materials, instructions, outcomes, and questions.

Figure 0-17: Course Guidance Code Network

D 6: Int_6 - 6:1 the level that I am at, I believe once the material is well laid out w... (413:638)

the level that I am at, I believe once the material is well laid out with clear objectives and instructions I am able to move on my own. As such I would need a forum where I

D 2: Int_2 - 2:22 Instructions that are clear and precise can also be helpful when it co... (3264:3377)

Instructions that are clear and precise can also be helpful when it comes to improving understanding in a Course.

D 5: Int_5 - 5:15 I felt that learning can happen face to face and virtually as long as... (7129:7262)

I felt that learning can happen face to face and virtually as long as there is clear guidance on what has to be done on the tasks.

Figure 0-18: Extract of Quotations on course guidance

Figure 4-18, quotations 5:15 and 6:1 reiterate the contribution of course guidance to learner self-direction. According to Moore (1997) participant 6 and 5 would easily fit in a highly structured course with minimal or no dialogue with the teacher. However, from Quotaion 1:15 and 4:3, there was little transactional distance in the course as learners communicated via emails and discussion forums.

“The platform influenced me positively in the sense that there is an opportunity for interaction with the tutor and other students through discussion forums. That aspect made me have a sense of belonging to a class” (Quotation 4:3).

4.3.4 Course Orientation

One of the critical aspects that the participants shared with the inquirer, was the importance of course orientation. More so that the course included use of technologies that they had not used before. These technologies included Turnitin (plagiarism checking application software), Blackboard (Learning Management System), student Portal (for results access, online registration access, class schedules, links to the other systems such as Blackboard etc.).

Figure 0-19: Course Technologies Orientation Code Network

The participants felt there was too much to learn especially for first time online learners who still had to familiarise with the university systems.

D 4: Int_4 - 4:10 Ideal the groups are fine but my experience in the course made me feel... (1844:2436)

Ideal the groups are fine but my experience in the course made me feel otherwise as group members were not forth coming. The benefits from group discussions were very minimal. I think the reason being that since most of the participants had challenges in the technology, they did not know how to access their groups. I suggest there be an orientation of how to use the platform prior to the actual subject content. It was challenging learning the content and subject matter simultaneously. It felt like tug of war but I think with the coming modules we would have gained the online experience.

The participants needed to be transitioned into online learning and they are coming from backgrounds where learning was through contact sessions. In Distance learning, learners are

fragile as it is easy for them just shut the laptop and not be learners anymore. Quotation 5:7, 4:10 and 4:19 amongst others shown in the course orientation network alludes to that.

D 4: Int_4 - 4:18 Group work is important but digital challenges made it difficult (4345:4409)
 Group work is important but digital challenges made it difficult

4.3.5 Technical Support

The participants also acknowledged the criticality of the technical support that they got from the Library Staff, the technical Department, and the Blended and Distance learning and the teachers. The code network for the theme is shown in Figure 4-20. The theme is dependent on the theme discussed in section on Course technologies Orientation.

Figure 0-20: Technical Support Code Network

One reason for the criticality of the technical support in the success of e-learning from the learner perspectives owes to the fact that the context in which the online distance learning delivery mode is sought has challenges of digital literacy as the adoption of the e-services usage by the target population is still at its nascent stages. As discussed in the chapter one and two, online distance learning is attractive to adult learners, the majority of who were exposed to the traditional face to face learning with access to technologies like TV, film, and radio. The challenges that they faced in using the institution systems led them to seek technical support from their teacher, Blended and distance learning (BDL), library, and technical departments. The teachers were their first point of contact in the classroom so they would pass through them in case they could solve the technical problems learners had; from the library personnel, they needed assistance on accessing the library systems such as Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) (See Screenshot for the webpage), passwords and virtual tour on accessing e-resources; the BDL department was for support on challenges in accessing Blackboard; and the technical department personnel was for support such as h/w and software problems.

 D 4: Int_4 - 4:17 The lecturers who had the technical skill enhanced my experiences as t... (4051:4337)

The lecturers who had the technical skill enhanced my experiences as they were on the go and had a way of saving us when we had a technical breakdown. Otherwise, lack of

OPAC screenshot

4.3.6 Course Interaction

The course interaction is captured briefly in Figure 4-21.

Figure 0-21: Course Interaction Code Network

Quotation 7:11 also suggests that the interaction changed compared to when they started using the discussion forum confirming that the technical skills of navigating the newly introduced systems were lacking but improved with exposure. The change in technology usage may also be attributed to the technical support that the participants applauded in the theme Technical Support. Hence the participants found the criticality of technologies orientation to the first years. The course interaction was through the discussion forum participation and participants claimed that the discussions helped them broaden their perspectives. The claim is evidenced in the quotation 1:20 in Figure 4-22. The same participant in quotation 1:21 alluded that “not only do learners learn from each other in discussion forums but they get to have a balanced analysis of issues”. Quotation 5:10 also gives emphasis on the post first approach before interacting with peers and the teacher.

D 1: Int_1 - 1:20 Some of the points which course mates covered in their discussions/ana... (5339:5578)

Some of the points which course mates covered in their discussions/analysis on the Blackboard helped me to think about the issues from different view points. That helped enrich my analysis of educational issues especially contemporary ones.

D 5: Int_5 - 5:10 There was communication in the modules such as LTA, ETE an RHE and PPA... (4454:5110)

There was communication in the modules such as LTA, ETE an RHE and PPA1. The lecturers were communicating via discussion forums roughly on time. Some discussions were very effective as you could feel that there were points to take home during the discussions from both the lecturer and the other peers. I enjoyed most the discussions where the teacher would ask further questions on what you would have said as it elicited more from me. I have developed to think critically. At time the ETE lecturer would ask you to make reference to the other peers post and share our views. This really made it look real that were in class though mediated by computers

Figure 0-22: Sample quotations from Course Interaction Code Network

On the other hand, the participants raised concerns of feedback from teachers that is not informative and delayed access to learning resources. The participants argue that these two are also critical in the success of distance learning. Feedback is meant to help learners achieve the targeted goals by informing the concerned learners on where they went wrong and how far were they from reaching the targeted goal. With the nature of distance learners, they get easily demotivated as they would feel isolated.

However, from the seven participants that were interviewed, only one participant brought the issue of access to intermediaries. Though not a critical success factor for distance learners, it is more of a requirement that the learners have access to the intermediaries. The participants mentioned that the communication media was adequate with emphasis from the quotation 6:7 that alluded to the communication media allowing communication from both the receiver and the sender. Inclusive of the communication media mention earlier on in this section, the participants mentioned the use of telephone, chats, and Skype for communication by both teachers and learners. However poor Internet connectivity was cited as a barrier.

4.4.2 D_Engagement

The D-engagement theme had codes such as Discussion, feelings of Isolation and communication adequacy as shown in Figure 4-24.

Figure 0-24: D-Engagement Code Network

The discussion code has also been discussed in the previous theme in section. The discussion forum was used as a tool for interaction. As learners participate in the forum, the exchange of text can take the form of dialogue, hence the appreciation by other participants that the discussions changed the way they view the world. As shared by the participants, in some of the modules, some activities were done collectively, requiring team effort. Quotation 6:14 reveals that the social aspect of learning.

 D 6: Int_6 - 6:14 As mentioned earlier, the course made be free to share my own views. I... (4888:5131)

As mentioned earlier, the course made be free to share my own views. I learnt a lot especially when some peers or the teacher critiqued my view .That made me learn that learning happens when we are in a group as I get corretetd where I am wrong

Figure 0-25: Quotation 6:14

The code, feelings of Isolation also generated findings that the dialogue between the learner and teachers and amongst peers could eliminate the psychological distance:

 D 4: Int_4 - 4:5 The platform influenced me positively in the sense that there is an op... (1256:1468)

The platform influenced me positively in the sense that there is an opportunity for interaction with the tutor and other students through discussion forums. That aspect made me have a sense of belonging to a class

Figure 0-26: Quotation 4:5

In a similar vein, quotation 6:12 echoed the same sentiment.

D 6: Int_6 - 6:12 It helped understand that we think and see things differently. At times... (4148:4457)

It helped understand that we think and see things differently. At times you like say to yourself...” Woow, I never thought of that” which for me made the discussions made me develop different perspectives . I developed a affinity to reading posts from particular students because that iswhere I got my motivation

Figure 0-27: Quotation 6:12

Not only was there interaction amongst learners and the teacher in some modules, participants claim that some questions were thought provoking and engaged them cognitively.

D 3: Int_3 - 3:14 in some modules where questions were thought provoking, you would see... (3460:3753)

in some modules where questions were thought provoking, you would see lots of traffic in the discussion forum especially where views were varying and needed academic debates. I remember in the Educational Technology module, the questions were challenging and needed us to put our heads together

Figure 0-28: Quotation 3:14

In cases of no participation in small group activities, some were no deterred as they worked independently driven by their zeal and motivation to complete the task/activity. This is reflected in Figure 4-29.

D 3: Int_3 - 3:23 Like I mentioned I am not an independent learner but when people never... (6560:6785)

Like I mentioned I am not an independent learner but when people never turned for participation in group tasks and discussion forum , my digital skills and literacy , search skills and my intrisinc motivations kept me going.

Figure 0-29: Quotation 3:23

However, quotation 3:10 argues that not all modules eliminated the psychological distance. Although in some modules, dialogue was intensive, in others there was little or total lack of dialogue. Most of the participants raised concern in lack of participation in small group activities.

4.4.3 D_Support

The theme housed codes such as encouragement, library support, teacher technical support, teacher support as shown in Figure 4-30

Figure 0-30: D_Support Code Network

The participants found all the codes in the network were very critical to the success of e-learning. The participants argued that encouragement played a critical role in the success of the e-learning course.

D 1: Int_1 - 1:18 As a lecturer myself, I know the importance of always encouraging stud... (4657:4960)

As a lecturer myself, I know the importance of always encouraging students to take studies seriously. So, yes the encouragement by lecturers that we take our studies seriously including actively participating on blackboard in terms of discussions contributed significantly to the success of the programme

1 Codes:

- Encouragement: contributed to success of course

D 3: Int_3 - 3:9 What I noticed was though some lecturers used telephones and emails to... (2236:2595)

What I noticed was though some lecturers used telephones and emails to communicate, they would use these rarely mainly for isolated cases like late submissions reminders, personal cases where as a student you decide to get mute maybe for reasons best known to oneself, weak performances and you needed encouragement. At times emails would be student initiated

D 2: Int_2 - 2:19 The teacher tried her very best in offering the much needed support to... (2877:2969)

The teacher tried her very best in offering the much needed support to each and every learner

D 3: Int_3 - 3:16 I remember in ETE, in some discussion forums each of of us would be as... (4203:4755)

I remember in ETE, in some discussion forums each of of us would be asked to create a thread sharing individual views prior to having access to peer posts. It was also a requirement to critique posts by other students and respond to the critiques in one's posts. This made be learn more and reflect on my posts to an extent that at times I would yield and accepts a different perspective from mine based on the constructive debates in the discussions. What I enjoyed most was the probes which got the best out of us and guided the discussions we had

D 4: Int_4 - 4:12 I used to get reminders from the lecturer encouraging me to participate... (2553:2928)

I used to get reminders from the lecturer encouraging me to participate. In the ETE module, the lecturer would even send supporting material in cases where as students we were challenged. I remember the file that the tutor sent on how to access the discussion

forums, and how to subscribe in the forums. She used screen shots in the mini support tutorials and that helped a lot

Figure 0-31: Encouragement quotations

Quotation 3:9 emphasis that encouragement in the course was for the cases that had challenges in the course. However, quotation 7:12 states that encouragement to all learners is a necessity to establish a connection with the virtual learners.

D 7: Int_7 - 7:12 The dialogue was good but I would prefer a situation where the lecture... (1946:2303)

The dialogue was good but I would prefer a situation where the lecturers call students at least once a month to maintain a good relationship, emotional connection with the students. Just like in face face we see the students on daily basis hence that rapport

Figure 0-32:Encouragement for all learners

More quotations on this network can be accessed in the Appendix

4.4.4 D_ Teacher Responsiveness

The theme had codes such as class size, teacher online presence, interaction, time managements and, feedback and timeliness. All these were found to play a critical role in the success of e-learning. The class size was influential in the teacher online presence and the quality of the feedback and its timeliness. The timeliness of the feedback was cited as having a role in the learners' time management especially when the goal to be achieved was dependent of the feedback. Once the feedback is delayed time management becomes strained according to the participants.

D 5: Int_5 - 5:9 Similarly the other students would not respond to other peers' posts.... (4075:4450)

Similarly the other students would not respond to other peers' posts. You know it is so demotivating that you are so motivated to post and get a quiet response. You begin to wonder whether you did the right thing or not. However , with my commitment and intrinsic motivation I needed some signal that I was in the right direction so I kept checking whenever I had the chance.

Figure 0-33: Teacher Responsiveness Code Network

4.5 Learner Autonomy

The learner autonomy theme had codes such as learner commitment, self-discipline, enthusiasm, motivations, time management, attitude towards technology and technology familiarity amongst others.

4.6 Summary

The chapter discussed the data collection and analysis process and how data saturation was reached. The codes in the hermeneutic unit were discussed and how there were arrived at. The next Chapter concludes the findings and communicates the recommendations.

Chapter 5: Discussion, Conclusions, and Recommendations

5.1 Introduction

The chapter discusses the findings and establishes the relationships existent between the ToD constructs in context. In addition the conclusion and recommendations for future studies are stated.

5.2 Findings

The findings were elicited from the three main constructs of the ToD. These are explained below:

5.2.1 Course Structure

The flexibility of distance learning allows learners take courses from remote areas, away from the institution from which the courses are offered. The MEd-HE programme from Botho University is an online programme that can attract a learner population from eclectic cultures. Hence, the development of learning material in diverse formats afforded each learner an equal opportunity to access and customise their learning. The flexibility of the course structure was found to be a critical success factor in e-learning. Of course, the course flexibility varies between programmes, however, it is equally essential that there is the responsibility on the part of the student even if the online courses are flexible. The participants argued that the submission dates of the assignments were on the same date but were communicated on time. Despite the timely communication of the dates some participants argued that they felt the pressure. To ease the pressure, the participants needed to be self-directed and be responsible for their own learning by managing their time and seek the teacher's support on time. However, [KLOPFENSTEIN \(2003\)](#) posit that regardless of age, it is the teacher's role, as a facilitator, to supporting the learner in assuming responsibility for learning such as providing opportunities for developing learner independence.

In terms of technical support that, the participants cited two types of support that they needed for the success of e-learning initiatives. These were the technical support that emanates from

- i. library,
- ii. technical departments for solving hardware problems
- iii. Distance learning department to solve LMS issues, teacher technical competency
- iv. technical support from teachers,

The institution has a physical library that is ideal for the learners studying through a face to face delivery mode and makes vast use of an ebrary that services both the learners in a F2F and online learning modes of delivery. The ebrary has e-resources such as e-books, databases such as Ebscohost and ProQuest, and subscribes to e-journals such as Emerald, Dawson era, and Jstor. In addition, the ebrary is coupled with systems such as OPAC which promotes the digital literacies in the institution.

As for the technical support from the technical department, it is expected that with devices and software that are used to access e-learning resources, learners and staff do face challenges at some stage and would require the technical assistance from the technical department. Botho University has a dedicated department (BDL department) to support the online learners with matters regarding the learning management system. These include enrolment, access to the learning material, and support on usage of the LMS tools not only to learners but to teachers as well. The department is the Help Desk for the Blackboard. Once the learners are enrolled, they may continue to face the challenges that may be solved by their teachers. The MEd-HE programme revolves around technology and requires some level of technological fluency. Because of the varying digital literacies and the expectations

that the institution and teachers has on their engagement with Online material, the learner found Technical support critical to the success of e-learning.

Course guidance, course orientation and course interaction were also found as critical success factors in e-learning by the learners. These came out strong as they are the map of the programme. Once the learners have the map, they may manoeuvre around the programme with minimal support from the teachers. The structure can be that which allows little or greater transactional distance and that would depend on those that play a role in making educational decisions including the teacher. Hence, the role of the teacher in putting the map together cannot be overemphasized.

5.2.2 Dialogue

The second construct of the Theory of Transactional Distance in the context of the study looked at four sub constructs namely e-intermediaries, engagement, support, and Teacher responsiveness. From the learners' perspectives, e-intermediaries were considered as critical for e-learning endeavours. However, in the study, that would not be considered as intermediaries are a requirement. The intermediaries are the facilitating condition, the technology is a medium of dialoguing. It cannot go without mention that the digital divide is a reality. The unequal access of smart phones, iPads, Tablets, Computers, and the internet does exist but does not make them critical.

The engagement, support, and teacher responsiveness were found to be critical for the success of e-learning. The Transactional distance is also determined by the relationship that is existent amongst the three main constructs of the ToD. If the structure is such that the TD is little, then the dialogue sub constructs such as engagement should be put in place by the teacher through

the materials that are accessed by the learners. In a cognitive constructivist perspective, it is the role of the teacher to engage the learners cognitively as they interact with the learning material. Deepening on the nature of the discipline and the teacher, learners can be afforded that opportunity to learn collectively in groups to allow scaffolding from a more able group member to take place.

As humans, we are social beings and it is how the teacher develops that social skill among learners. The teacher support plays a part also to guide the learners to the desired goal. No matter the level of autonomy the learners are at, that support from the teacher should be there to assure a sense of belonging in virtual environments. For example, the participants raised the issue of delayed teacher and peers' responses on discussion forums, those responses should be given in a timely matter to keep the other person interested and to moderate their line of thinking where necessary. Besides, support should not only be taken as needed when one has challenges in life, but also to establish that connection that you have with learners in a face to face lesson. One participant said

right is shea

The dialogue was good but I would prefer a situation where the lecturers call students at least once a month to maintain a good relationship, emotional connection with the students. Just like in face face we see the students on daily basis hence that rapport should be maintained online through telephonic conversation to elicit more about the student experience

The transcript shows that all learners need the support of their teachers. What the learners was requesting here was to dialogue with the teachers at individual level. This could be taken to elicit the individual experiences from learners especially if there is no provision of a forum that captures that.

5.2.3 Learner Autonomy

As part of the findings that study brought to fore that the transactional distance is influenced by the extent of the autonomy the learner has. Considering all conditions put in place, the willingness and commitment of the learner to participate and interact with the teacher, peers and the content is critical. There were mixed views on the submission dates of assignments being on the same date for three modules. Some learners reiterated that it takes time management, self-discipline and self direction to cope in a virtual learning environment.

Also learner familiarity with the technology came up strong among participants. It is expected in a multi cultural environment that learners have varying learning abilities, cultures, learning styles, and also varying levels of technology, media and information literacy. Considering that at the beginning of the programme that learners got exposed to a lot of institutional systems and had to alter their practical understanding of technology and behaviours, it is how this experience is handled at institution level and at classroom level. It is important, as the participants alluded, that course orientation be considered as critical. All the subconstruct of learner autonomy were found critical to the success of e-learning.

5.3 Conclusions

The success of e-learning depends on varied factors in different contexts. In terms of transferability it cannot be concluded that the findings in their entirety are valid in other contexts as the research design followed a sampling logic. The study sought to understand critical success factors elicited from the learners of one selected institution as consumers of the educational services. The findings showed that the critical success factors in e-learning include course flexibility, course guidance, course interaction, course orientation, technical support (library, technical department, BDL department), teacher support, teacher responsiveness,

learner engagement, and learner characteristics (self-direction, self-discipline, motivation (intrinsic) , commitment, willingness to learn, technology familiarity).

The study focussed on one institution offering distance learning programmes in Botswana. However, generalisation of the results may be difficult since the sample size was small. Hence the aspect of generalisation to other contexts might be very difficult to achieve as the samples in the qualitative research are very low. However, the findings would help in generating a theory that might then need to be tested in other contexts for generalisations. The resources that are used in each context may vary, hence these when taken into consideration in other future researches may help endorse the generality of the expected theory.

5.4 Recommendations

The study has given insights into post-graduate learner perspectives on e-learning in the context of a selected institution in Botswana using a qualitative approach. The nature of a qualitative research deals with very small samples that are not representative the postgraduate students in Botswana because they are not exposed to the same learning environment, different approaches to teaching, different learning resources, and infrastructure amongst other conditions. In this regard, it is recommended that these findings in the study are validated using a larger quantitative sample. Alternatively, since each institution's operations and environment vary, a similar study could be carried out with a different institution to ascertain the consistency of the results.

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Appendix A: Application for Research Permit

Botho University
Box 501564
Gaborone

21/11/2016

The Manager

Ministry of Ministry of tertiary Education, Research, Science, and Technology
Gaborone
Botswana

**REF: APPLICATION FOR A PERMIT TO CONDUCT RESEARCH (TERESA
CHIKEREMA STUDENT ID xxxx)**

I Teresa **Chikerema** a holder of a passport whose number is **XXXXXXX**, is a student at Botho University. I am pursuing MEd in Higher Education. This letter serves as an application for a research permit to conduct research entitled “**Critical Success Factors in e-learning in Higher Education: Learner Perspectives**” as a partial fulfilment of the above mentioned programme.

The varying learner demographics, the advancement of technology and the increasing need to access higher education has necessitated the move from a traditional to a contemporary learning environment marked with the use of technology as a delivery strategy. As such, the study seeks to understand the key antecedents that contribute to the success of e-learning in a developing country with mention of Botswana. The focus is on the learners’ voices as the consumers of the educational services. The findings of this research are expected to inform policy frameworks, higher education leadership intending to adopt the e-learning initiatives at their institutions and least but not last, the enhancement of the learning experiences. In as much as the study is focusing on Botswana, the expected findings are expected to contribute to the literature of e-learning and Distance learning in the developing community and would also have implications to the enhancement of the phenomenon though contexts may differ.

The inquirer is expected to collect data from learners at BOCODOL and Botho University including those that have dropped out to gauge the factors. The participants will be drawn only from the Gaborone campuses.

The consideration of this application would be appreciated.

Yours Sincerely

Teresa Chikerema

Appendix B: Research Permit

TELEPHONE: 3655400/3655483
TELEX: 2944 THUTO BD
FAX: 3914271

MINISTRY OF TERTIARY EDUCATION,
RESEARCH, SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
PRIVATE BAG 00516
GABORONE

REF: E 1/20/2 (10) Temp

19th January 2017

Ms Teresa Chikerema
P O Box 501564
Gaborone

Dear Madam

RE: APPLICATION FOR RESEARCH PERMIT

Reference is made to your application on the above captioned matter.

Your application for Research Permit for the proposed research titled '*Critical Success Factors in e-learning in Higher Education: Learner Perspective*' has been granted for you to conduct a research in Botho University and BOCODOL University. The permit is valid for one (1) year. You are kindly advised to peruse section 4.4 to 5.0 of the 'Guidelines for Application for Research Permit' in Botswana.

Any changes in the proposed research should be communicated, without fail, to the Permanent Secretary, Ministry of Tertiary Education Research Science and Technology citing above reference.

By copy of this letter, the Director of Research Science and Technology is advised to take note of this development and ensure that deliverables to government are timely met.

Yours faithfully

Dr Theophilus Mooko
Permanent Secretary

cc: Dr Morgen Chawawa
Research & Consultancy Department Manager

16885

https://t.me/16885 | Private Bag 005 Gaborone

Appendix C: Consent Form

Consent Form

My name is **Teresa Chikerema** a student at Botho University pursuing MEd **in Higher Education** qualification. My Student ID is As a partially fulfilment of the qualification I am conducting a research entitled: **Critical Success Factors in e-Learning in Higher Education: Learner Perspectives** in which you are expected to provide data on.

Purpose of the study: The purpose of the study is to understand what makes e-learning successful from your perspective as a learner in distance learning mode. It is my understanding that you are currently enrolled as a distance learner at (Name of the Institution).

Benefits of participation: The expected benefits of your participation are two-fold. Firstly, by agreeing to participate in this research means that you are making your voice heard as a distant learner and your needs are going to be represented in the outcome of the project. Secondly, the findings of this research are intended to inform decision making by leadership in our Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and policy makers in relation to distance learning initiatives in the community in which we are part of.

Incentives for Participation: Participation in the study is on voluntary basis, no incentives will be provided.

Procedure: You are requested to sign this consent form as a confirmation that the purpose of the study and how the data will be used has been explained to you. If you are happy with this, you can go ahead and sign the form.

Withdrawal from Participation: You can withdraw at any point of data collection if you feel uncomfortable. Please note that none of your personal details or the data you provide for this study will be used for other purposes.

Recording: The interview can be recorded: Yes No:
(Tick what is applicable to you)

Declaration:

I have read and understood that I am free to ask questions or withdraw from participation without penalty. None of my demographic or sensitive information that I will disclose in this study will be used for other purposes

Name of Participant *Signature of Participant* *dd/mm/yyyy*
Date

Appendix D: Interview Protocol

Interview

As a distance learner, you will note that you do interact with the teacher, peers, and learning material using various technological tools. The experience that you have in the electronic learning environment is influenced by the interplay of three constructs namely:

1. Course Structure,
2. The Dialogue, and
3. Learner Autonomy(Independence)

coupled with other external factors that affect them in the endeavour to reduce the psychological distance between you, peers, and the teacher. This study seeks to uncover what exactly you think contributes to the success of e-learning from your own point of view. It need not be one element of a learning environment but a combination of these based on the lived experiences in the course(s) you are enrolled in. It could be something that you may not lay a finger on but eventually as you answer the interview questions your perspectives will unfold and these will help the academic fraternity and leadership improve on your educational experience.

Firstly we will start with the demographic questions followed by more specific questions.

Part A. Demographic details

- i. Age: _____
- ii. Gender _____
- iii. Level of Education (e.g. *Post graduate, Undergraduate*) _____
- iv. Year of Study (1st, 2nd, 3rd, etc.) _____
- v. How many courses have you done Online / distance mode (successfully) _____ (unsuccessfully) _____
- vi. Gender of Teachers (*No. of Females*) _____ (*No. of Males*) _____
- vii. Have you ever been a dropped out in any one of the courses in question v.?
- viii. Are you employed (*Yes/No*) _____

Part B Course Structure

- i. Briefly describe in your experience what you would consider a successful e-learning course?

Probe: What have been the strengths of the course that made you hold on to your hopes that you can make it?

- ii. Describe your experience in what you would consider an unsuccessful e-learning course?

Probe: What have been the weaknesses or challenges in this journey that affected the way you learn online?

- iii. In your experience, how does a course flexibility and content quality influence the success of e-learning?
-

Probe: Think about the quality of video, audio components, PowerPoint Presentations and self- learning material in the course, do they leave you having some sense of isolation from the teacher?

- iv. The nature activities, exercises, or assessments in the course, is it challenging, thought provoking?
-

Probe: Does the nature of the assessments develop in you the skills that needed in the 21st century (e.g team work, analytical, problem solving , critical thinking skills)

- v. Given that the online courses are often offered through the learning management Systems (such as Blackboard, Moodle, WebCT etc), how did this platform influence your attitude towards e-learning?
-

Probe: Think of examples that you felt isolated from your peers or teacher because of the platform

- vi. Did you at one point in the course feel like the course did not put your needs into consideration at the time of designing the course?
-

Probe: Think of examples where you feel the pacing, tasks, the lack of clarity of requirements and goals by the teacher disengages / demotivates you from participation

Part B Dialogue

- vii. Normally the communication media that is used for communication includes the email, discussion forums, chat, videos, and telephone. To what extent do you feel that the communication medium that is used in the courses that you are talking are of excellent quality or appropriate?
-

Probe: Think of examples where you preferred that you teacher/ class would use a different medium that one than the one in use

- viii. Was there communication with your teacher in the course? Describe the ways in which you communicated with your teacher? How has this communication helped you understand the study?
-

Probe: How do you feel about the quality discussions throughout the course?

- ix. Describe how you feel about working in groups? Did you participate in any? Were the other students forthcoming in the groups?
-

Probe: How has this interaction with your peers contributed to the success of the e-learning? Did you learn from them or you preferred working as an individual?

- x. Did your teacher(s) ever post thought-provoking questions online or do they design interactive tasks in the course syllabi?
-

Probe: How has this interaction with your peers contributed to the success of the e-learning? Did you learn from them or you preferred working as an individual?

- xi. How do you feel about the support of the teacher elicitation of student interaction? How did it influence the success of your study?
-

Probe: In what way did the encouragement from the teacher lead to active involvement of learners in the course?

- xii. How does the quality of discussion in the course make you understand the study?
-

Probe: Share examples of how the frequency of positive interactions contributed to the success of the study?

- xiii. To what extent did the dialogue change your attitude toward e-learning? Share examples.
-
-

Part C: Learner Autonomy

- xiv. To what extent has the course afforded you the skill to construct your own explanations form the given tasks?
-

Probe: How important is it to have the guidance of the teacher in doing activities or tasks? How confident are you in finding explanations on your own? Of what influence was it to your study?

- xv. How confident are you in managing your time, meeting deadlines, and taking responsibility of your own learning?
-

- xvi. **Probe:** Do you always find excuses for not doing your work in the course?

Part D: Other

- xvii. Please comment on how the teacher's technical skill or ability to operate the learning platform enhanced your learning experience?
-

- xviii. Please comment on what is important, group success over Individual success? How did this influence your progress in the course?
- xix. What role do your attitudes toward technology and motivations play in the success of e-learning?
- xx. How has the technical support received during the course improved your attitudes toward e-learning?

Appendix E: Sample quotation for the D_Support networks

D 4: Int_4 - 4:12 I used to get reminders from the lecturer encouraging me to participate... (2553:2928)

I used to get reminders from the lecturer encouraging me to participate. In the ETE module, the lecturer would even send supporting material in cases where as students we were challenged. I remember the file that the tutor sent on how to access the discussion forums, and how to subscribe in the forums. She used screen shots in the mini support tutorials and that helped a lot

1 Codes:

- teacher support

D 4: Int_4 - 4:17 The lecturers who had the technical skill enhanced my experiences as t... (4051:4337)

The lecturers who had the technical skill enhanced my experiences as they were on the go and had a way of saving us when we had a technical breakdown. Otherwise, lack of the technical skill from the teacher affected our participation as it was easy to just shut down the machine / laptop

2 Codes:

- teacher support / ○ teacher technical skills: supportive

D 4: Int_4 - 4:20 The support has greatly increased my appreciation for e-learning. As a... (4534:4922)

The support has greatly increased my appreciation for e-learning. As a distance learner, I have appreciated the amount of effort that is required from the teacher to get the students working. I personally used to have a negative attitude on students with challenges on Blackboard but I have experienced appreciated the anxiety that they go through when they are brushed aside by the tutor.

3 Codes:

- teacher support / ○ teacher technical skills: supportive / ○ Technical Staff: Library not supportive

D 5: Int_5 - 5:5 I didnt know but I emailed my lecturer who responded to me on how to ge... (2048:2332)

I didnt know but I emailed my lecturer who responded to me on how to get to the group and reach my group members. She followed that response with a Blackboard

announcement on the same issue to the rest of the group. But still some would not participate for reasons that I do not know